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Modelling of pollutant reduction by vegetation in open road conditions

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Abstract text

People residing along the major roads are prone to air pollution. Green interventions such as vegetation barriers, trees, hedges and green walls are effective in reducing pollutant concentration near open roads. These vegetation interventions lower pollutant exposure by enhancing dispersion and removing them through deposition and absorption. Moreover, scientific planning of vegetation barrier along open roads leads to improvement of downwind air quality (Abhijith et al., 2017). This study aims to quantify the dilution and dispersion components of pollutant reduction occurs behind green barriers. For this investigation, we will conduct field measurement campaigns to evaluate benefits of near road vegetation. The data obtained from the experiments will be used for modelling studies to determine pollutants deposited/absorbed and dispersed in presence of green interventions. The modelling studies will be carried out by employing computational fluid dynamics software openFOAM. Furthermore, we will assess effects of vegetation parameters such as height, thickness, and leaf area index on deposition and dilution of pollutants. Overall these anticipated findings will help in formulating practical recommendations on planting vegetation barrier under near road conditions.

Motivation

This research is motivated by the importance of separating the deposition and dispersion components of pollutant reduction by vegetation through modelling studies.

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References

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